
Administrative Problems & Strategies of Marathi Newspapers (With Reference to Nashik)

Dr. Shelar Balu Ambadas

Associate Professor, Dept. of Commerce, K.T.H.M. College, Nashik.

Corresponding Author – Dr. Shelar Balu Ambadas

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Abstract:

Marketing of newspaper is now a days is difficult task before the management. Newspapers entertain the people and give knowledge to them. To start and run a newspaper is not easy job. It needs huge capital investment and lots of efforts. Trained, skilled and talented manpower is required. One should have capacity to bear the losses for so many years. Patient is required. Beside this, modern technology, best services, different and qualitative news is the demand of this business. Those who fulfill these conditions can stay here. That's why common man cannot afford to start newspapers. Only industrialists and politicians who have black money can enter in this business. Today, the cost of production is increased to such a height that the old and well-established newspapers also rethinking about their business. Administration expenditure is also high. If one wants to continue his newspaper, he requires qualitative staff which demand attractive salary. The main source of income is commercial and government advertisement. Income from circulation can't meet the expenditure. A single copy of newspaper costs for Rs. 10 to 15. Because of advertisement it is affordable to sale for Rs. 3 to 4. The loss of new edition is covered by the profit earning editions in other cities.

Introduction:

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Present Newspapers in Nashik:

Daily Gavkari:

There are very few reputed local newspapers in Nashik. Gavkari is one of the oldest local Marathi newspapers not only in Nashik but also in the state. Dattatrya Shankar Potnis started this daily on 1st January 1938. It used to publish from Malegaon in the beginning. It was weekly. Due to some

reasons, it winds up its business for two years from into Daily Gavakri. It started its business from Manmad. Famous journalist of Daily Lokmanya P. V. Gadgil from Bombay joined Gavkari. That time Gavakari launched other publications like Lokmanas, Krishi Jagut, Saptahik Rasrang, Amrit, Day view. Evening Sadnand. This group also continued weekly Gavkari. Gavakari group have started its editions from Jalgaon, Dhulia, Nagar and Thane. Due to good service, variety & better quality than other, this group became very popular. The magazine Amrit had lots of demand not only in Nasik but throughout Maharashtra. Editor Manohar Shahne gave his Midas touch to this magazine. No other magazine could compete with Amrit. To give information, knowledge & joy are the prime objectives of newspaper. Gavakari proved it.

Because of quality, Gavakari was the brand name in journalism. It was popular among all class. Weekly Rasrang also got large readership. It was the first weekly in Marathi language which was devoted to movies, drama & art. Now days competition is unavoidable. There is little chance of survival. Variety and quality without higher price are the demand of readers. At the same time cost of production have increased. Problems like labor, machines, technology & no doubt competition, forced to change the old policies of Gavkari. The regional newspapers are launching new schemes for readers every day. New packages for the agents, newspaper sellers, new schemes for advertisement agencies are offered by regional newspapers. This resulted to change the face of local newspapers. Malpractices, politics entered in this industry. This also affected the Gavkari. The oldest newspaper's like Gavakari which was top at once upon a time in Nasik, is now at sixth position in case of circulation.

The revenue from advertisement is also reduced which forced Gavkari to compromise at every level. Gavkari has

given well known journalist to the Marathi journalism. P. W. Gadgil who was working with `Lokmanya` (Bombay) worked as editor of Gadkari. Old & new generation of journalist is the donation of Gavkari. It was social institution once upon a time. It worked as mouth piece of Gandhian in north Maharashtra. It created awareness amongst rural & urban people during the independence struggle. Now days it helps many people & organizations. It gave helping hand to the people of Marathawada after tragedy of earth quake. `Ajantha` was sister concern of Gavkari & publishing from Aurangabad.

Daily Deshdoot:

Deshdoot was started in 1970 in the presence of founder editor of Sakal, Dr. Nanasaheb Parulekar. News Media is the weapon of politicians & industrialists. Knowing this importance, noted industrialist Devkisan Sarda launched `Deshdoot`. At present Vikram Sarda is the Managing Editor, while Sashikant Tembhe is the Editor. Nishikant Bhalero is Executive Editor. Pradip Niphadkar is also having same post. Deshdoot hav completed thirty-two years. During this journey it faced many problems. Before four years age related to Shri Ram & Seeta, which was largely criticized. Society at large was hearted by this dirty article. Suresh Avadhoot was editor at that time. Angry readers attacked the offices of Deshdoot in Dhulia, Jalgaon, Nasik from that stage, the circulation came down.

In Marathi, Deshdoot is the first daily which tied up with another publication i. e. Chitrlekha. Deshdoot & weekly Chitrlekha started the scheme for readers in north Maharashtra. Along with the Sunday Deshdoot, chitalekha use to circulate to the readers. The price on that day was five per copy. One year this experiment went on. It was getting good response from readers. Deshdoot also started evening daily Matantar, but is closed down shortly. The

other experiment like supplement for women class (Najrana) science supplement, got good response. But due to some reasons the science supplement closed down. Today there is Sunday supplement, news supplement, supplement on movies & Majorana.

Bhramar-Evening Paper:

Bhramar is popular amongst the small businessmen, auto driver & the people who want to pass the time. The price is two Rupee. In Nashik First Evening Daily is Bhramar. It is publishing from Panchavati, Nasik. It is the first evening daily in the Nasik. Chandulal Shah started this daily. It used to publish twice in a month. But from 1972 it converted into evening daily & now celebrating 40th year. Efforts to start this daily are really admirable. There were four two pages till yesterday. Today, there are four to six pages in two rupees, which is good progress. There is no strong competitor to this paper. Mahanagar was there but it had no demand.

Since last 50 years Bhramar is enjoying the monopoly. Simple lay-out is the feature of Bhramar. Another feature is, no color or black white supplement. The daily jock 'Sukakath Masala' is very popular among the readers. There are demerits of this evening daily. Many time it publishes fake or bogus news without confirming it. This helps in increasing superstitions. Journalist should have general knowledge which includes current affairs, Science, Commerce, Arts, Politics, Sports etc.

Daily Sakal:

Sakal was started by great editor Nanasaheb Parulekar, in 1932. Sakal have given new direction & dimension to the Marathi newspaper industry. The name 'Sakal' was suggested by a student of Fergusson College, Kashinath Bhide who was from Dhule. He got the prize for that. Hundreds of names were suggested throughout the state. Due to the hardwork, perfect planning, importance to the Common

Man, Sakal became very popular & could progress rapidly. Fresh & special news, particular lay-out, balanced news, super printing technology, color printing, variety in the matter are the main features & power of Sakal. Sakal Times, Gomantak, Sakal Saptahik, Agro-one, Magazine Tanishka, Sam Channel are the publications of Sakal group.

The speed of progress of Sakal is really admirable. Sakal group have started separate editions from Mumbai, Kolhapur, Nasik, Aurangabad, Jalgaon, Goa, Nagpur and Solapur. Sakal is not behind in social work also. Kargil war, Marthawada earthquake are few examples when sakal collected funds for the victims. At present Sakal ranks second in case of circulation in Maharashtra. Lokmat ranks first. But considering the quality Sakal is on the top. Keeping the same policy & quality Nasik Sakal edition started on 17th March 1989. Dawarkanath Lele was the editor followed by Uttam Kamble. Now Dr. Rahul Ranalkar is editor. Nashik Sakal covers the north Maharashtra including Nasik, Jalgaon, Dhulia and Nandurbar editions. There are separate offices at these places. There are regional offices at Malegaon & Sinnar. For advertisement, there is office at Ashok Stambha, Nasik. Main office is at Satpur.

Daily Lokmat:

Lokmat is one of the fastest growing newspaper in India. For public relation T.V., Radio & newspaper is very useful. Public relationship of Lokmat is very good. It is ranked first in case of circulation in Maharashtra. It is at number one place in Nasik also. In North Maharashtra, Lokmat Group launched first edition at Jalgaon. Later it moved to the Nashik. Now there are more than 13 editions publishing from all over Maharashtra. In Maharashtra, Lokmat is the largest circulated Marathi daily. As per the Indian readership survey (1999), readership of Lokmat was 70 lakh 60 thousand. Sakal was at second place (37 lakh

30 thousand) followed by Loksatta (32.10 Lakh), Navakal (27.8 Lakh) & Times of India (16.6 Lakh). In case of readership Lokmat stands seventh at national level. From 17th Aug. 2002. Lokmat started to publish in 27 inches size, mostly all the newspapers are in this size now a days. This age is collaboration age. To expand and to run the business, tie up is essential thing now a days. Lokmat have tied up with the English daily. The Asian Age which is one of the popular newspapers in India. This newspaper will co-operate Lokmat Group. In case of circulation in Nashik city, this edition ranks first. In North Maharashtra, Lokmat ranked first having circulation of one lakh 72 thousand 419 copies per day. (Data as per Audit Beauru of circulation July- December 1999). The elaboration of data is like below- Nasik Edition 62 thousand 819, Jalgaon Edition 76 thousand 751 & Ahmednagar Edition 32 thousand 849.

Daily Diya Marathi:

Bhaskar is published throughout 64 cities in the country at a time. In India, Bhaskar Group is well-known Media group. In Hindi language, it is most circulated newspaper. In this language, it has many chain newspapers. Ramesh Chandra Agarawal is the chairman. The main office is at Bhopal. In north India various editions are published. Its total circulation is 35 lack copies per day. To expand the business, this group has started Marathi daily in Maharashtra called Diya Marathi. It was launched in Aurangabad on 29th May 2011. From 3rd July 2011, Nasik edition was launched. Before starting Nasik edtion, Bhaskar group undertook survey. This was regarding how should be the ideal newspaper, expectations of the readers, which news are read more. Considering readers opinion, design of Divya Marathi was prepared. Because of its policy, quality and content, this paper is now a leading newspaper in Nasik. The circulation is 65

thousand copies per day. Other reason is that is provides 12 pages daily with District and City supplement with main issue. Diya Marathi have started Ahmednagar, Auranagabad, Jalgaon, Nasik, Solapur, Akola, Amravati editions. and now preparing for Mumbai and Pune. English, Gujrati, Hindi and Marathi editions are now published regularly. Rasik, Education and Mahurima are the mazagines of this group.

Daily Maharashtra Times:

Times, Express Group launched its Marathi daily, Loksatta from Bombay, while Free Press group started Navashakti in Marathi. Times Group is well known Media House. Maharashtra Times is the publication of Times of India. These institutions have more than 150 years tradition. In 1947, British owners of Times of India gave away the ownership to Ramkrishna Dalmiya, which later on transferred to Jain group. Economic Times etc. Main competitor of Then Chief Minister of Maharashtra, Yashwantrao Chavan suggested Times Group to start its Marathi daily. Hence on 18th June 1962, Maharashtra Times came into existence. D. B. Karnik was the first editor. Govindrao Talwalkar, who had good experience in Loksatta, joined as Assistant Editor in Maharashtra Times. D. V. Gokhale who was in Navshakti, joined as news editor. Money & mechanical help was availed by Times Group. So, a qualitative newspaper was borned. On the very first day, 70 thousand copies of Maharashtra Times were printed which finished within few hours. Due to good quality, Lay-out, fresh news, Maharashtra Times posed challenge before other newspapers. Maharashtra Times was the first newspaper, which devoted full page to sports news. It also started first, to review the classical music. Maharashtra Times did not start supplement like sports, movies & other publications what Sakal, Loksatta and other newspapers did. But still this newspaper is popular due to various reasons. It includes

best Lay-out and presentation, different kind of news, good quality of the news print, simple but impressive language, fresh news and photographs. But it does not give importance to the rural problems, so it is not popular at village level. For daily newspapers, there is an excess supply of persons seeking jobs. That excess supply is 4 to 1.

Daily Loksatta:

Loksatta is well known newspaper which belongs to Indian Express Group. It is not printed in Nashik like Maharashtra Times. Both papers are printed in Mumbai and published in Nashik. India Express group is one of the largest in newspaper industry in India. English Editions are published from Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, Ahmedabad etc. There were editions in Tamil, Telgu, Kannad, Gujrathi languages. So, the need to start Marathi daily felt. And in the year 1948, Loksatta started in Bombay. Navakal, Lokmanya, Navshakti & Prabhat were the main competitors that time. Only Navakal & Prabhat were belonging to Marathi owners. Weak economic condition was the main problem of the above newspaper. Loksatta had a support from Express Group. So, it started in good format. News network, technology was superior. So, the circulation at beginning was very high. Lay-out, quality news & fresh subjects as well as news, excellent editorial department, aggressive marketing were the features of Loksatta. So, in few years, it became number one in Maharashtra. Now it ranks third. It is popular in Mumbai. At present its circulation is above five Lakh copies per day. Lokmat is at number one place followed by Sakal. Trimbak Parvate was the first editor of Loksatta. He & Madhavrao Gadkari gave new face to this newspaper should be balanced & accurate.

Daily Pudhari:

Pudhari is not famous for its aggressive & outstanding writing but it is known as balanced newspaper. Daily

Pudhari started Nashik Edition Recently. From 1st January 1939, Pudhari started as a daily in Kolhapur. It used to publish as weekly. The first issue of this weekly was published on 13th May 1937. This newspaper is one of the largest selling & popular in Marathi language. Pudhari is published & printed in Kolhapur & having more than two lakh circulation per day. Ganpatrao Jadhav is the founder of Pudhari. He started newspaper called Sevak in Kolhapur before Pudhari, which was the foundation of today's Pudhari. When weekly Pudhari started in 1937, V. T. Patil was editor, G. D. Patil was publisher & S. B. Bhosale was printer. But the main editorial responsibility was with Ganpatrao Jadhav. He was the financier also. Attractive Lay-out, colourful printing, all kinds of news, various supplements are the important features of Pudhari due to which it has created challenge before the competitors like Sakal, Lokmat etc. Today, Pudhari is the reputed newspaper in not only Kolhapur but in Maharashtra also. Pudhari has started its edition in Pune but it is not having good response, as expected. Other newspapers started their editions from important cities e. g., Mumbai. But Pudhari could not do it. So, it is not popular like Sakal, Loksatta, Lokmat. When Pudhari started in 1939, daily Vidya Vilas was the main competitor. Today Sakal and Lokmat are the main competitors. Since its formation, Pudhari was fighting for common man especially non-Brahmin. Due to this policy, it faced economic crisis at the initial stage. The main founder, Kolhapur Newspapers Association also closed down. Due to 1942 freedom movement, condition of Pudhari became very serious. Ganpatrao Jadhav accepted the responsibility on 12th December 1943. He also accepted the responsibility to repay the loan of Pudhari. He passed in this test & today a good newspaper is running successfully. The main source of income is

used for expansion of the Pudhari & this is the secret of its success also.

Daily Punya Nagari:

The State level newspaper Punya Nagari is published from Mumbai & circulated in Mumbai, Ratnagiri, Nasik, Nagar and Pune. Its regional offices are in these cities. This newspaper is considered for the research here, because this newspaper has greatly affected local newspapers wherever it is circulated in the state. News appeared in this newspaper are mostly strange and fake. But there is a class of readers in Nasik & in other cities who like to read this kind of news. There is no requirement to train the reporters because they are not expected to give qualitative news. The only aim of this newspaper is to make time pass. There are no skilled Sub editors. This newspaper has good demand in Nasik & rural areas. Price is rupee one & pages are eight. So, people purchase it. Higher & middle class of the society in Nasik don't purchase this daily because it has no value.

Marketing Strategies of Marathi Newspapers in Nashik:

1. Reduction in Prices:

Marathi dailies have embarked on a price war in Nashik, Kolhapur, Pune and Aurangabad in an effort to boost circulation and, consequently, use this to garner a larger share of advertising. In Nashik, Lokmat sold its papers for Re.1 at the time of Launching. Lokmat, Sakaal, Pudhari and Punya Nagari have cut back cover prices since January to boost circulation and attract advertisers. In Kolhapur, Sakaal which is published by former Union minister Sharad Pawar's nephew Abhijit Pawar's **Sakaal Media Group**, recently slashed its cover price from Rs. 3 to Re.1. Pudhari, run by Pudhari Publications Pvt. Ltd, now sells at Rs. 2 compared with Rs.3 earlier, while Lokmat and Punyanagari have dropped their cover

prices from Rs.2 to Re.1. All the price cuts have come in the past six weeks.

Sakaal and Punyanagari have also lowered prices in rural Pune and Aurangabad. Lokmat, too, costs Re.1 in Pune now, against Rs.2 earlier. Lower cover prices means losses in subscription revenue for the newspapers, estimated to add up to Rs.50 crore this year. It also means the publications boost circulation, which could help them grab a larger share of the advertising market for Marathi dailies, expected to grow by 25% this year, according to a publisher who did not want to be identified.

2. Branding:

A cult in general notion is a sect or group or a faction. Like religious cult that attracts thousands of devoted disciples, certain brands have magnetic characteristics. They attract die-hard customers who will be devoted to the brand. Brand cult is defined as a phenomenon where customers display an unusually strong emotional involvement with a particular brand; thus, lending the Brandan exceptionally high degree of customer loyalty, along with an amplified sense owning the brand. Sakal, Maharashtra Times and Lokmat uses this strategy. Cult branding creates an experience, a feeling an aura of a group identity- involving the customer in a way the employs them. Consumers become passionate and empowered about the cult brands. If a product or a brand fulfils this desire of a person, the customers become a core loyal to the brand/product. This serves as the basis for Brand cultism. Some of the remarkably successful and powerful cult brands are Harley Davidson, Apple computer, vans shoes, etc. Bullets, Ambassador, AMUL, and Khadi are some of the commonly referred cult brands in India. All the cult brands have the customers with fiery passion and fierce loyalty towards the brand.

3. Marathi Newspapers on Web:

Marathi Newspapers on web is recent strategy of Marathi newspapers in Nashik. The newspapers are mirror of society and also the agents of social change and the creators of attitude and situations. They conduct companies, carry on propaganda. Influence and educative voters, canalize public opinion and mould government policies. Now a day's Marathi newspapers also have begun to use the modern technology to publish online papers. The press also makes a direct and visible impact on the functioning of the administrative and political systems of the country. It provides comprehensive and objective information on all aspects of the country's social, economic, political and cultural life. Newspaper brings every person into touch with active world. As mahatma Gandhi said "one of the objectives of a newspaper is to understand the popular feelings and give expression to it, another is to arouse among the people certain desirable sentiments and third is fearlessly to expose popular defects.

4. More Page Average:

More pages of newspapers than normal are known as more pager average. Generally, Marathi newspapers provide 10 pages of main issues and 4 pages of supplement in Rs.5. To capture the market share, Newspapers provide 12 pages of main issues and 6 pages supplement in same price. This is effective strategy to raise number of readers. In nashik, Diya Marathi, Lokmat providing such facility. Sakal is also trying same. This strategy has affected the market share of to greater extent. Local newspapers are going to close down. Because, readers compare their newspapers with Lokmat, Sakal.

5. Local Level reporting:

Mumbai and Pune represent two facets of Marathi journalism. Pune's Sakal, in spite of its recent shift towards new marketing and management strategies, still

remains imbued with idealism of the nationalist period and its emphasis on wide-ranging local-level reporting. On the other hand, in Nashik's highly segmented market, smaller newspapers claim popularity due to their unpredictable mix of business sense, technical mastery and cultural intimacy. Spreading across India after the end of the 'emergency' in 1977, technological change in the form of the personal computer and offset press revolutionized the newspaper industry. The circulation of daily newspapers in all languages trebled between 1976 and 1992 - from 9.3 million to 28.1 million and the dailies-per-thousand people ratio doubled - from 15 daily newspapers per 1,000 people to 32 per 1,000. Regular reading of something called "news" both indicates and causes change. Expansion of competing newspapers clearly signals the vitality and growth of capitalism: newspapers have owners and owners must have advertisers. The changes of the past 20 years are obvious yet largely unstudied.

6. Bumper Gifts to the Newspaper Sellers:

Management of newspapers in Nashik uses this tactic or strategy to increase their readership and circulation speedily. Almost all state level newspapers give various gifts to the newspaper's sellers. Sakal and Lokmat provides Steel Stalls, Bags, Umbrellas, caps, raincoats to sellers. Sakal had provided group insurance to the sellers few years ago. Parties to the sellers are now a days are common.

7. Attractive commission to Advertise Agencies:

Revenue is most important for any kind of business. Newspapers are also not exception to this. In Nashik, there is association of Advertisement Agency. They avail advertise to the newspapers. Cost to produce newspapers is increasing day by day. So, the management of Marathi newspapers maintain healthy relationship to the Advertise Agencies. Newspapers management awards schemes to the Ad

Agencies. More commission is given to these agencies which result in more business revenue generations.

8. Facilities to the Newspaper Sellers:

Newspaper sellers are the key factor in sell of newspapers. Marathi newspaper management of newspapers in Nashik uses this strategy to increase their readership and circulation speedily. Almost all state level newspapers give provides various facilities to the newspaper seller. Regular Health checkup camps, felicitation of newspaper seller and their children are also some strategies in Nashik by Sakal, Lokmat, Divya Marathi. Local newspapers are not in such a race their sell has come down.

9. Various Events for readers:

As an effective marketing strategy, newspaper management organize various events for the readers. Sakal organize state level Sakal Drawing competition every year since decades. Sakal also competition for housing societies in nashik on the basis of Home Minister show on Zee Channel. To attract the yong readers, Sakal also entered in the college world by starting Yin club which works for personality development. Lokmat organize Premier cricket league like IPL of BCCI. Lokmat honours the reputed and well-known experts in various fields giving Lokmat Awards. Every newspaper in Nashik organizes big functions on their foundation day. Maharashtra Times organize Happy Streets on Sunday which includes various old games, music, stalls etc. This gets tremendous response. This paper of Times groups also organize Matta Heritage walk which includes visits to historical places in Nashik. Daily Deshdoot organize Property fair which invites

10. Various supplements, columns for various class:

In Nashik, state and local newspapers have started various supplements with main newspapers. It is the part of marketing strategy to raise the circulation and revenue. This suppliments

targeted various sector of the society. Agriculture supplement of Deshdoot papers and Agro one newspaper of Sakal is for farmer readers. Entertainment supplement or page is there of every newspaper. Beside this, Sunday supplement, supplement for women and youths, science supplement is there. Columns like puzzle, reader letters, column like opinion of readers, future, gossips in bolly woods, political criticism, new book arrival, senior citizens experience etc.

11. Collaborations and new ventures:

To stay in competition and capture the market share, management of Marathi newspapers have tied up or entered into collaboration or started new ventures. To start news channel is very costly. Lokmat newspaper started IBN Lokmat news channel with national level IBN channel. Sakal has launched its own marathi channel known as SAAM T.V. Pudhari newspaper recently launched news channel called as Pudhari channel.

12. Help of social media:

Today is the age of modernization and social media. Newspapers collects the news and print it. But the news is publishing next day which becomes stable or old. News channel has created serious challenge before newspaper industry. So, to provide fresh news, now a days almost all Marathi newspapers have started e-newspapers and web newspapers. They are active on social media. Sarkarnama of Sakal newspaper, Lokmat online portal, Matta website are example of it.

13. Attractive salary:

Every industry and organizations are run and progress with help of talented and skilled manpower. Newspapers are not exception to this. For hiring the service of talented news reporter, sub editors, editors, marketing and administrative staff newspaper invest funds. These talented man power is offered attractive salary, facilities by management. This skilled staff is

provided training also. To stand in the competition, established newspapers like Lokmat, Sakal, Divya marathi offered higher economic package to the competitor newspapers and higher them. This is great loss to the concern newspaper.

14. Job Contract System at every level:

To run newspaper is very challenging job now a days. Reason is high cost of operation and production as well as selling. Single copy of a newspaper cost more than 20 rupees. But due to cut throat competition, it is sold just for rupees five per copy. The income of five rupees again shared with newspaper seller as a commission rupee 2 per copy. Remaining 3 rupee bears other cost like salary, marketing, printing paper and ink, machine etc. So, to achieve the target of profit, newspaper management now a days accepted the policy of contract system at every level. From attender to manager and from reporter to editor, everybody is offered job on contract system. Permanent job is dream. There is no job security. This is contract is for 11 months, 3 years and likewise.

17. Compromise with unethical factors:

Management of some newspaper compromise with unethical factors. If a political leader or builder cut the tree illegally or engage in malpractices and corruption, newspaper editor does not publish news regarding this though it is his duty. The reason is that, these corrupt people are advertisement partner of newspapers. So, the main pure purpose of journalism is violated. Such kind of malpractices is great loss to the society and democracy.

18. Remote control of political leaders:

To start and run newspaper/ news channel and achieve target of profit is not easy job. Many businessmen launched newspaper and channel but failed to survive. Newspapers was mission before independence now it is run for commission only. Reputed newspapers are owned and run by political leaders as well industrialist. They control newspaper directly and indirectly. Editor and manager can not work independently and freely. They are forced to compromise with corrupt people. So, while drafting and launching marketing strategy, there is interference of remote control.